

Analysis of The Usage of The Shopee Live Streaming Application, The Effectiveness of Promotion on Customer Repurchase Decisions Mediated by User Satisfaction

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the impact of live streaming, promotion effectiveness, and user satisfaction on customers' repurchase decisions, based on data from 105 respondents through an online questionnaire. The analysis focuses on both direct and mediated effects, with quantitative methods applied.

The results reveal that live streaming significantly enhances user satisfaction (p-value = 0.000), but does not have a direct effect on repurchase decisions (p-value = 0.084). Promotion effectiveness, while not significantly impacting user satisfaction (p-value = 0.103), does have a significant influence on repurchase decisions (p-value = 0.032).

User satisfaction plays a crucial role in driving repurchase decisions (p-value = 0.038) and mediates the effect of live streaming on repurchase behavior (p-value = 0.049). In contrast, promotion effectiveness does not significantly influence repurchase decisions through user satisfaction (p-value = 0.184).

This study underscores the importance of user satisfaction as a key mediator in encouraging repurchase behavior. E-commerce platforms should enhance the engagement and familiarity of live streaming, ensuring it aligns with users' shopping habits. Moreover, promotional strategies must be tailored to customer expectations in order to increase satisfaction and reduce disappointment. By optimizing these aspects, platforms can better cultivate customer loyalty and drive repurchase decisions.

KEYWORDS: Live Streaming, Promotion Effectiveness, Repurchase Decisions, User Satisfaction.

I. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology in the digital era has brought significant changes to various aspects of life, including how people shop. The presence of online shopping applications provides convenience for consumers to meet their needs without having to visit physical stores while supporting fast delivery services. This contrasts with the traditional shopping system, which requires direct interaction between sellers and buyers.

The COVID-19 pandemic has further accelerated the shift in shopping behavior. Large-scale social restrictions (PSBB) forced consumers to switch to online shopping, while sellers who previously relied solely on conventional methods had to adapt to digital platforms. This shift presents both a major challenge and an opportunity for businesses to leverage technology to reach consumers. In Indonesia, e-commerce platforms such as Shopee and Tokopedia have become the primary choices for the public. Shopee ranks first with annual visits reaching 2.35 billion in 2023, far surpassing Tokopedia with 1.25 billion visits. This data indicates that Shopee's dominance is inseparable from the innovative features it offers, including Shopee Live Streaming.

Figure 1. Shopping Application Platform Data Table 2023

Source : (databoks.katadata.co.id)

Shopee Live Streaming is one of Shopee's flagship innovations that allows sellers to provide real-time product information, offer discounts, and promote products interactively. This feature not only helps customers make purchasing decisions but also provides a competitive advantage for sellers to increase their sales.

Figure 2. Data on the best-selling live streaming online shopping platforms in 2023

Source : (databoks.katadata.co.id)

Promotion effectiveness is one of the key factors in e-commerce competition. Strategies such as massive discounts and collaborations with brand ambassadors are often relied upon by platforms to attract consumer attention. Shopee, for example, collaborates with famous K-Pop idol groups like Blackpink to strengthen its brand image while attracting more loyal customers. On the other hand, user satisfaction is also an important indicator of the success of online shopping platforms. Positive consumer experiences when using the application impact their loyalty to continue using the platform. In the context of increasingly fierce competition, online shopping applications must continue to innovate to remain relevant and maintain their market share.

The phenomenon of Shopee as a leading e-commerce platform in Indonesia is an interesting subject for further research. Specifically, how features such as Shopee Live Streaming and the effectiveness of promotional strategies influence customers' repeat purchase decisions. By considering user satisfaction as a mediating variable, this study aims to provide a deeper understanding of the impact of digital innovation on consumer shopping behavior.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Live Streaming

Live streaming is one of the interactive features in online shopping applications that allows sellers and buyers to communicate in real-time. During live streaming, sellers can showcase products directly, provide detailed explanations, and answer customer questions through the comment section. This method is considered more effective as it builds customer trust in the products offered compared to mere photos or product descriptions. Technological advancements in the digital era have influenced shopping behavior. Buyers tend to look for practical, easy, and fast ways to find products, while sellers compete to create innovations to stay competitive. Businesses that fail to follow market trends or introduce new features, such as live streaming, are more likely to be displaced. Through live streaming, buyers can evaluate products in real-time, such as checking materials, colors, or sizes, even though they cannot physically touch the products. This provides a more authentic experience and encourages customers to make purchases. This feature also enables buyers to receive exclusive promotions available only during live streaming sessions, such as additional discounts, cashback, or direct gifts.

Promotion Effectiveness

Promotion effectiveness reflects the ability of marketing strategies to attract customer attention, increase purchase interest, and ultimately influence purchasing decisions. With the advancement of technology, promotional media are no longer limited to television, radio, or print but have shifted to digital platforms such as social media and online shopping applications.

Social media serves as a very effective promotional medium due to its extensive reach and ability to attract customer attention through creative visual content. For example, Shopee utilizes story ads or video ads on Instagram and TikTok to promote major events, such as the 12.12 discount campaign, thereby attracting more customers to use their application.

In addition to visual promotions, digital payment systems also play a significant role. Ease of transactions, such as the availability of COD (Cash on Delivery) or Shopee PayLater, makes customers more comfortable and confident in making purchases. The combination of creative promotions and convenient digital transactions enhances promotion effectiveness, making it more appealing to customers. Shopee also leverages public figures or celebrities as brand ambassadors to strengthen the app's image. Brand ambassadors with large fan bases, such as K-pop groups, can attract more customers and increase trust in the platform.

User Satisfaction

User satisfaction is the key to success in building customer loyalty. Satisfaction arises when customers feel that the products and services provided meet or exceed their expectations. In the context of Shopee, user satisfaction can be influenced by various service features, such as the chat feature, help center, and the app's presence on social media. The chat feature allows buyers and sellers to communicate directly about the products offered. Through this feature, buyers can ask questions, clarify product information, or negotiate prices directly. Additional features such as image galleries, money transfers, or emojis make communication more interactive.

Shopee also provides a help center supported by chatbot technology to offer quick solutions to common customer issues, such as refunds or shipping status. Additionally, customers can contact Shopee via email or phone for more personalized service. However, user satisfaction is not only influenced by customer service but also by the overall experience of using the application, including response speed, transaction security, and product conformity with descriptions provided.

As to Badriyah (2015), job satisfaction is defined as an employee's sentiments or perspectives about positive or negative aspects of their employment that align with the opinions of their coworkers. A favorable opinion or assessment of one's own work is what Robbins et al. (2018) define as job satisfaction. Job satisfaction, broadly speaking, is the degree to which a person is content with their work and workplace. Managers must prioritize a supportive atmosphere by listening to staff issues and objectives, taking action, or encouraging team building in order to boost health workers' motivation and job satisfaction (Bonnenberger et al., 2014). According to Badriyah (2015:241), a number of elements, including pay, advancement, supervision, extra perks, awards, work policies and procedures, coworkers, the task itself, and communication, affect job satisfaction.

Purchase Decision

A purchase decision is the final process of consumer consideration after evaluating their needs, seeking information, comparing products, and assessing their benefits. In e-commerce, purchase decisions are influenced not only by price or product quality but also by the overall shopping experience. The purchase decision process begins with need recognition when consumers realize a

specific need that must be met. Subsequently, consumers search for information about products that can meet their needs. This information can be obtained through customer reviews, product evaluations, or recommendations from friends and family. After obtaining the information, consumers evaluate various products based on factors such as price, quality, and benefits. During this stage, promotions or positive reviews from previous customers can significantly influence their decisions. Ultimately, consumers decide whether to purchase a product based on their evaluations. This process can be influenced by past experiences, trust in the platform, or the product's suitability to their needs. satisfaction.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework for this study is as follows, based on the review that was received :

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: Author, 2024

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses two types of data: primary and secondary. Primary data is collected through online questionnaires distributed via Google Forms, eliminating the need for direct interaction with respondents. Meanwhile, secondary data is gathered from references such as journals, books, theses, and relevant online sources to support the research discussion.

This research is quantitative, analyzing collected data to test the relationships between variables using a quantitative research model based on Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) with the Partial Least Square (PLS) approach. This method is used to identify complex relationships among variables. Additionally, descriptive analysis is performed to illustrate the observation results from respondents based on the distributed questionnaires. This approach is expected to provide accurate and in-depth results regarding the influence of Shopee Live Streaming features on customers' repeat purchase decisions mediated by user satisfaction. investigation.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondent Characteristics

The respondents studied were 105 people, with the majority being female (59%), under 25 years of age (51%), and an average income of Rp. 1,000,000 to Rp. 6,000,000 (43%).

Table 1. Respondent Characteristics

Characteristics	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Man	43	41%
Woman	62	59%
Age		

<25	54	51%
<35	43	41%
<45	6	6%
<55	2	2%
Average Income		
<Rp. 1.000.000.-	4	4%
> Rp. 10.000.000.-	32	30%
Rp. 1.000.000.- s/d Rp. 6.000.000.-	45	43%
Rp. 6.000.000.- s/d Rp. 10.000.000.-	24	23%

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

Outer Model Analysis

Figure 2. PLS Algorithm Structural Model.

Source: Author, 2024

In measuring the output outer loading, a correlation above 0.7 is needed. The results of the convergent validity output figure above, it has shown validity above 0.7 and has met the requirements.

Table 2. Average Variance Extracted

	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Live streaming	0,579
Promotion Effectiveness	0,557
User Satisfaction	0,617
Purchase Decision	0,673

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

Next is the Average Variance Extracted (AVE). This test can be said to be valid if a construct has reached a value of >0.5. In table 4.6 above, the AVE value is above 0.5. This has been declared valid. So that the testing of discriminant validity on all variables has been achieved and meets the requirements.

Table 3. Composite Reliability

	Composite Reliability
<i>Live streaming</i>	0,846
<i>Promotion Effectiveness</i>	0,790
<i>User Satisfaction</i>	0,865
<i>Purchase Decision</i>	0,892

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

This test is seen through the accuracy and reliability of each answer obtained through the questionnaire that has been distributed from time to time. Consistent and unchanging data can be said that the answers from the distribution of the questionnaire are reliable. Measurement of this variable can be seen through the composite reliability coefficient above 0.70. Based on the measurement of the reliability test above, it can be stated that it is reliable because the value is above 0.7.

Inner Model Analysis

Inner model testing can be tested through R-Square. This measurement can be seen through the criteria that are considered good. Criteria 0.75 (high), Criteria 0.5 (medium), Criteria 0.25 (low).

Table 4 R-Square Test Results

	R-square
Purchase Decision (Y1)	0,353
User satisfaction (Z)	0,482

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

From these values, it can be explained that the percentage of the purchase decision is 35.3% and 48.2% of user satisfaction. While the remaining 64.7% of purchase decisions and 51.8% for user satisfaction are influenced by other factors that are not included in this model.

Table 5. Hypothesis Test Results: Direct Path Coefficients

Hypothesis testing will be done through bootstrapping on the Smart PLS 4 program. This test will be seen through P-Values <0.05. P-Values > 0.05 are considered to have no significant effect on other variables.

	Original Sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
X1 -> Z1	0,585	0,589	0,111	5,253	0,000
X2 -> Z1	0,153	0,157	0,121	1,268	0,103
X1 -> Y1	0,188	0,184	0,136	1,381	0,084
X2 -> Y1	0,237	0,248	0,128	1,848	0,032
Z1 -> Y1	0,229	0,230	0,129	1,778	0,038
X1 -> Z1 -> Y1	0,134	0,134	0,081	1,652	0,049
X2 -> Z1 -> Y1	0,035	0,037	0,039	0,900	0,184

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

Based on table 5 above, it shows that of the 7 hypotheses above, 4 results have a significant influence with P-Values < 0.05 and 3 results have no significant influence with P-Values > 0.05.

1. Live streaming (x1) has a positive and significant effect on the User Satisfaction variable (z).
2. Promotion Effectiveness (x2) does not have a positive and significant effect on the User Satisfaction variable (z).
3. Live streaming (x1) does not have a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1).
4. Promotion Effectiveness (x2) has a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1).
5. User Satisfaction (z) has a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1).
6. Live streaming (x1) has a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1) mediated by User Satisfaction (z).
7. Promotion Effectiveness (x2) does not have a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1) mediated by User Satisfaction (z).

Discussion

H1 = Live streaming (x1) has a positive and significant effect on the User Satisfaction variable (z). This means that this is most likely due to live streaming, products can be seen and displayed directly to customers. So when the product received is in accordance with what is seen during the live streaming, this can increase the satisfaction of users who shop through the features in the application.

H2 = Promotion Effectiveness (x2) does not have a positive and significant effect on the User Satisfaction variable (z). This means that the promotion delivered is most likely not always successful in influencing customers. Even if the promotion does not match the expectations that have been formed through the promotion, it can cause the promotion to fail, so it does not affect the level of user satisfaction.

H3 = Live streaming (x1) does not have a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1). This means that although live streaming provides a visual experience and information about the product, it is not strong enough to influence customer repurchase decisions. This is likely because most of the characteristics of the respondents do not fully understand or feel familiar with shopping via live streaming on the Shopee application.

H4 = Promotion Effectiveness (x2) has a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1). This means that the effectiveness of promotions can have a significant influence on Customer Repurchase Decisions through various discounts, flash sales or vouchers available.

H5 = User Satisfaction (z) has a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1). This means that the higher the user satisfaction given through their shopping experience, the more likely they are to make repeat purchases.

H6 = Live streaming (x1) has a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1) which is mediated by User Satisfaction (z). This means that live streaming can increase repeat purchase decisions when customers see positive reviews or experiences from other users who are satisfied. This shows that user satisfaction is an important factor that strengthens live streaming on Repeat Purchase Decisions.

H7 = Promotion Effectiveness (x2) does not have a positive and significant effect on the Customer Repurchase Decision variable (y1) which is mediated by User Satisfaction (z). This means that the effectiveness of promotions alone is not strong enough to influence Repeat Purchase Decisions through user satisfaction. Although promotions can attract customers' attention, if the products or reviews that customers see are not good or do not meet the expectations that have been formed from the promotion, then user satisfaction will not be created. This will ultimately have an impact on low customer interest in making repeat purchases.

V. CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate that live streaming has a positive and significant effect on user satisfaction. This reflects the ability of the live streaming feature to provide a visual experience that increases customer trust, especially when the product received matches the one displayed. However, live streaming does not have a significant direct effect on repurchase decisions. This means that although this feature provides clear information and an attractive visual experience, it is not strong enough to encourage customers to make repeat purchases, especially for customers who are less familiar with shopping via live streaming.

On the other hand, the effectiveness of promotions does not have a significant effect on user satisfaction. Promotions that do not meet expectations tend to fail to increase customer satisfaction. However, the effectiveness of promotions has been shown to have a positive and significant effect on repurchase decisions. Discounts, flash sales, and vouchers are the main attractions that can

motivate customers to make repeat transactions. This shows that an attractive and targeted promotional strategy is very important to increase customer loyalty.

User satisfaction itself has a very significant effect on repurchase decisions. This finding confirms that the more satisfied users are with their shopping experience, the greater their chances of making repeat transactions. Satisfaction is a key element in building customer loyalty and creating long-term relationships between customers and platforms.

In addition, live streaming also has a positive and significant influence on repurchase decisions through the mediation of user satisfaction. This shows that satisfaction plays an important role in strengthening the impact of live streaming on repurchase decisions. In contrast, the effectiveness of promotions does not show a significant influence on repurchase decisions through the mediation of user satisfaction. Although promotions can attract customers' attention, if the resulting product or shopping experience does not meet expectations, satisfaction is not created, and this ultimately reduces the likelihood of repurchase. Overall, this study confirms that user satisfaction is a central element that mediates various factors, such as live streaming and promotions, in driving repurchase decisions. Therefore, e-commerce platforms need to ensure that every customer shopping experience is able to provide optimal satisfaction to build loyalty and increase repurchase behavior.

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